

Symptoms Based Disease Prediction Using ML Algorithms

Ashish Wilson

PG Scholar

*Master of computer Applications
Amal Jyothi college of Engineering,
Koovapally, Kottayam, India
ashishwilson2022a@mca.ajce.in*

Ajith G.S

Asst. Professor

*Master of computer Applications
Amal Jyothi college of Engineering,
Koovapally, Kottayam, India
gsajith@amaljyothi.ac.in*

Abstract— The modern approach of health care is to detect the disease early instead of going for treatment after full diagnosis. Earlier, doctors use a risk calculations to diagnose the disease. Medical conditions, life routines, and more are used to estimate the risk of a disease. Mathematical methods and tools are used for calculations. The low accuracy rate is the challenge. But with the latest development of technologies like machine learning, disease prediction can be achieved with more accurate results. Doctors work with statisticians and computer scientists for developing better tools for finding diseases. Experts in this field work in identifying, developing and optimizing machine learning algorithms and models which will provide accurate predictions. For an accurate model, data can be collected from studies, health records and more. The number of dependent variables used is the difference between the traditional and ML approach. They only consider very few variables in old approach and age, weight, height, gender and more are not considered (due to computational limitations). Machine learning can be considered with many variables, which leads to better accuracy of health care data. Samples of records of 4920 patients diagnosed with 43 diseases were selected for analysis. Out of 134 autonomic variables that are severely related to disease, 95 (symptoms) were selected and optimized. This test work shows the framework of disease prediction created using machine learning types such as Naive Bayes, Random Forest, KNN and Decision Tree. This paper will present a study of results of machine learning algorithms.

Keywords— Machine Learning, Decision Tree, Random Forest algorithm, KNN, Naive Bayes

I. INTRODUCTION

Data mining is required in the medical and clinical fields today. At this stage, when some information mining strategies are used properly, important data can be removed from the large data set, which will help in the early selection of the clinical professional and further development of the welfare regime. The spirit is involved in the arrangement to help the doctor.

Diseases such as dengue, impetigo, diabetes, migraine, malaria, jaundice, and chickenpox greatly affect a person's well-being, and sudden death can occur whenever they are

neglected. The medical care industry can settle for a remarkable choice by digging into the vast database of information they have, for example by distinguishing secret examples. Additionally, connections in the data set. Information mining calculations such as Decision Tree Classifier, KNN, Random Forest Classifier, and Naive Bayes Calculations can address these current situations.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

A lot of research has already been done for the prediction of diseases based on various symptoms with the help of machine learning. Some references are:

A diagnostic model based on multiple symptoms [1] using a machine learning approach was prepared using a combination of different indicators of 41 diseases using the clinical records of 4920 patients. We identified 95 indications out of 132 side effects to avoid excessive fitting. From these results, they can conclude that each of the three models works well in the dataset. Unlike the other two models, Random Forest Classifier works well.

Another disease prediction model based on symptoms using a machine learning approach [2] discusses ML's techniques used for diagnosing various diseases like heart disease and diabetes. Most of the models has given excellent results because they specifically describe the characteristics. Previous studies have shown that SVM is 92.60 percent better at diagnosing heart disease. Naive Bayes is an accurately diagnosed diabetic condition. It provides 94% of the highest accuracy.

Kidney disease is one of the most serious diseases and requires correct diagnosis for better treatment. Chronic Kidney Disease Prediction Model based on symptoms [3] using a machine learning approach help to use different machine learning classifier algorithms with which the doctor can diagnose and treat the disease in a timely manner.

Liver disease is more common in most people. If we can diagnose the disease using the symptoms, the disease will get better care and treatment. Methods for detecting liver disease in patients using machine learning techniques [4] are suggested in this paper. SVM and logistics regression are used as two machine learning techniques in this paper. Using these models, the forecast analysis is performed and their performance is evaluated. The probability of prognosis of liver disease is achieved with 94% accuracy. In the future, the current situation will

be comparable to other technologies such as Naive Bayes classification and random forest.

The diagnosis and prognosis of cardiovascular disease requires a more accurate and precise diagnosis because a small error can lead to fatigue or death. There are many cases of death related to the heart and their number is increasing day by day. The cardiac prognosis model based on symptoms[5] using machine learning is essential for awareness of the diseases to deal with the problem. Algorithms for predicting heart disease used in this paper is K-Nearest Neighbour, Decision Tree, Linear Regression and Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithms. In this KNN gives a more accurate result.

III. METHODOLOGY

From an open-source dataset, we created a CSV and listed all the symptoms of the respective diseases there. Symptoms are then specified as part of the dataset, depending on the disease. We have listed over 230 diseases with more than 1000 unique symptoms. An individual's symptoms are used as input to different machine learning algorithms and the most accurate machine learning algorithm is used for prediction. It also recommends doctors for related diseases based on the predicted disease.

Fig. 1 Disease Prediction Model

- **Input the Symptoms**
We assumed that the user had a good idea of the symptoms he was experiencing while building the model. The built-in forecast considers 95 features, and the user has the option to enter as their own processing input.
- **Data preprocessing**
Data preprocessing is a data mining approach that converts it into encoded raw data in a form that we easily interpreted by an algorithm.
- **Data Cleaning:** Clears data through methods such as Fixing Missing Values and Filling Missing Value.
- **Data reduction:** When managing large databases, analysis is too difficult. As a result, we eliminate any independent variables (symptoms) that have little, or they will have no effect the target variable

(disease). In this study, 95 of the 132 symptoms closely related to the disease were selected.

- **Models selected**
Four algorithms are used to train the system to predict diseases:
 - K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) Algorithm
 - Naïve Bayes Classifier
 - Disease Tree Classifier
 - Random Forest Classifier
 At the conclusion of the work, a comparative study will be , comparing with the performance of different algorithm and comparing the accuracy of each algorithm.
- **Output**
When the system is trained using a 'training set' using the above techniques, a rule set is created, and when 'user attributes are entered into the model, these features' are processed according to the established set of rules, causes classifications and predictions.

The machine algorithm used for this paper are:

A. K-nearest neighbors (KNN)

The K- nearest neighbors (KNN) calculation is a type of supervised study. It basically works at a distance from other information, highlighting any preparation data of interest. The distance is kind of Manhattan. After this, K selects the nearest information to any number. In conclusion, it allows information that highlights the class in which most K information is focused.

Weighted KNN is a variant of KNN. At KNN we select the boundaries of an integer, and using those boundaries, we find where the expected core values are. In any case, if the value of k is assumed to be very low, the calculation for the focuses on the defects is very precise. Also, if the value of K is too large, then each is very closest to the K worth and the less weight to the focuses that were farther away. We had the option to get the most noteworthy precision utilizing this model. Likewise, among all the KNN models, this model gave us the best outcomes.

Minkowski distance formula.

$$d = \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - y_i|$$

B. Naive Bayes

Naive Bayes algorithm method which is using a supervised learning algorithm. It is based on the Bayes theory and is used to solve taxonomy problems. It is used in text classification that includes high-dimensional training datasets. The classifier is the simplest and most effective way to build a fast machine learning model that makes fast predictions. Property. The primary use is to perform text classification that includes a large number of training data sets.

The naive Bayes algorithm is based on the Bayes

$$P(s/h) = \frac{P(h/s)P(s)}{P(h)}$$

theorem:

Where

P(s)-Class prior probability

P(h)-Predictor Prior probability

P(s/h)-Posterior probability

P(h/s)-Likelihood

C. Decision trees

This is a decision tree-based categorization model that matches the tree's structure. It's similar to an if-then condition. The Decision Tree will learn a sequence of explicit if-else rules on feature values (in this example, symptoms), breaking down the dataset into smaller and smaller subgroups, and predicting a target value (disease).

Decision nodes and leaf nodes make up a decision tree.

- Decision Node: The decision node has two or more branches. Here, the symptoms are treated as decision nodes.
- Leaf Node: A leaf node will be represented as the decision classification of any branch. In this case, the disease is mapped to the associated leaf nodes.

A. ID3 Algorithm:

This one of the core algorithm which can be used in our work in the ID3 algorithm which was invented by J.R. Quinlan. ID3 uses a top-down approach, a greedy search algorithm through the given columns, and the user selects the attribute by checking the node in each column (attribute = symptoms), one of the beats for classification from the given set. ID3 entropy and information gain are used to select the symptom that can make a decision tree.

- Entropy: Because it measures the predictability of particular events, entropy is a measure of 'uncertainty' or irregularity. Using the frequency tables of each attribute, we'll need to calculate two types of entropy for a decision tree:
- Entropy E (c): In a frequency table, the current condition of the results is denoted by the attribute C, and the probability of occurrence of c is denoted by the attribute p (h):

$$E(C) = \sum_{h \in H} -p(h) \log_2 P(h) \quad (1)$$

- Entropy E (C, A): It employs a C and A frequency table, in which C denotes the current state of an attribute and A p (h) denotes the chance of an attribute H occurring.

$$E(C, A) = \sum_{h \in H} [p(h) * E(C)] \quad (2)$$

- Information Gain: The achievement is represented in the data by a state IG (C, A) changing its entropy after acquiring the attribute. In terms of entropy, it has changed (decreased) in relation to the symptoms.

$$IG(C, A) = E(c) - E(C, A) \quad (3)$$

D. Random Forest:

The Random Forest classifier is a user-friendly and flexible machine learning approach that gives excellent results without requiring hyper-tuning. The decision tree's primary flaw is overfitting. The information from

the trees will be stored in memory. Random Forest is a synchronisation research version that solves this problem. Ensemble learning refers to the use of many algorithms or the same algorithm over and over again. A random forest is the name for this form of decision tree. The more decision trees in the random forest, the better the result.

Random Forest work as follows:

1. From the given dataset of medical records, we will select K symptoms from a total of m symptoms, and then use the k symptoms to build a decision tree.
2. We repeat the process n times to create a decision tree with n random combinations of k symptoms (another random sample of data called bootstrap sample)
3. We have the total projected n diseases from the n-decision trees after passing each n-built diagnosis tree through a random variable to predict the disease
4. The projected disease's vote will be calculated, and the most predicted disease will be chosen as the random forest algorithm's final prediction.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULT

Different machine and learning models were used to check the prognosis of the disease for the available input dataset. Based on the level of accuracy, the disease with the highest accuracy predetermined will be finalized as a disease. The doctor then recommends the treatment or precautions for the disease.

Fig 2. Design ui for disease predictor

Fig 3. Result of disease predictor using symptom

After training, each algorithm's accuracy score was:

TABLE 1. ACCURACY SCORE TABLE

Algorithm	Accuracy
K NN	0.93294
Naïve Bayes	0.93341
Decision Tree classifier	0.95179
Random Forest	0.96121

V. CONCLUSION

Machine learning's advancement and applicability in the medical and health fields have enabled complicated data analysis through the use of simple straightforward machine learning algorithms. This research gives a comparison of the performance of four algorithms in a medical record, with up to 96.19% accuracy. The accuracy score is used to evaluate performance. Based on the disease the doctor is recommended, the disease with the best accuracy score will be finalized from the dataset.

We may infer that all four techniques function well on the supplied dataset after conducting calculations. When compared to four algorithms, however, Decision tree, Random Forest is giving better. On predicting the disease one can start treatment with needed medicines. Also this model will reduce the cost of diagnosing the diseases and recovery of diseases.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

The doctor's knowledge and experience are required because of other factors such as from medical records to weather conditions, atmosphere, blood pressure and numerous alternative factors. Currently, only less number of diseases are in the dataset. The scope of the dataset need to be improved as analysis, cleaning and delivery of data takes time. Past history of the disease is not considered. This can be included in future works. Now prediction is completely based on symptoms, and factors like age, climate are not considered. Existing system predict the disease but will not predict the subtype of the disease. So local diseases should be added that can improve the scalability. A centralised system can be designed by

providing unique id numbers to the users for better usage of data. Medicines can be displayed along with the medicine recommended by the doctor for comparison. The uploading facility of the reports of tests recommended by the doctors can be added to get better consultation experience

REFERENCES

- [1] Evaluation based Approaches for Liver Disease Prediction using Machine Learning Algorithms by C.Geetha/Assistant Professor, Dr.AR.Arunachalam - Jan. 27 – 29, 2021.
- [2] Symptoms, Based, Disease, Prediction, Using, Machine, Learning, Techniques, by, Dr., P. Hamsagayathri., Mr., S., Vigneshwaran, 978-1-6654-1960-4/21/\$31.00, ©2021, IEEE, (ICICV, 2021),.
- [3] Prediction, of, Chronic, Kidney, Disease, - A, Machine, Learning, Perspective, by, PANKAJ, CHITTORA,, SANDEEP, CHAURASIA-, February, 1,, 2021
- [4] Heart, Disease, Prediction, Using, Machine, Learning, Algorithms, by, Archana, Singh., Rakesh, Kumar (ICE3-2020), Disease, Prediction, Using, Machine, Learning, PRIYANKA, J., PANCHAL1,, SHAEZAH, A., MHASKAR2,, TEJAL, S., ZIMAN3, AUGUST_2021
- [5] Disease, Prediction, Using, Machine, Learning, PRIYANKA, J., PANCHAL1,, SHAEZAH, A., MHASKAR2,, TEJAL, S., ZIMAN3, AUGUST_2021